

ON-STREET PARKING AND SUSTAINABLE TRAFFIC FLOW IN YENAGOA METROPOLIS

¹Ezekiel Ovuokerie Gunn and ²Clement Ebizimor Deinne

Corresponding Author's Email: ovuokerie2001@gmail.com

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

¹Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

²Department of Geography, Faculty of Social Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

Abstract

Aside street trading, On-street parking constitutes one of the major impediments to sustainable traffic flow in many Nigerian cities. The dearth of research of on-street parking in Bayelsa State makes it imperative to examine on-street parking and sustainable traffic flow in Yenagoa metropolis. A convenience survey research design was utilized. A volumetric count of vehicles at different road junctions and streets revealed the dominance of tricycles followed by cars and mini-buses. Results revealed that there was a significant variation in the occupation of respondents, access roads and parking spaces with F values of 5.540, 7.347 and 4.979 at 0.05 level. The binary logistic regression revealed that lack of access to residence and parking spaces are 1.8 times and 1.2 times more likely to influence on-street parking. This study recommends efficient of-street parking management, construction of well-designed and planned off-street parking facilities, sidewalks and road setbacks to improve street space for pedestrians, strengthening the planning and institutional framework for development control and enhance sustainable traffic flow within Yenagoa metropolis.

Keywords: On-street parking, traffic flow, survey research design, binary logistic regression, Yenagoa metropolis

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Yang, Hao and Lei (2010), Victoria Transport Policy Institute (2011), and Ye, Chen, Wang, Zheng and Zhang (2013), parking is the act of stopping a vehicle and leaving it unoccupied for more than a brief time. Parking on one side of a road is commonly permitted, but on both sides of a road is often with restrictions. Parking facilities are constructed on most highways, to facilitate the free flow of traffic. Obot, Etim and Atser (2009) stated that in Nigeria as elsewhere cars are one of the dominant modes of transportation, urban circulation is one of the most obvious problems and parking seems to be an overlooked element of

transportation development. Litman (2023) stated that a typical automobile is parked 23 hours each day and uses several parking spaces each week. Parking facilities are essential components of a transportation system. They are also costly; for all dollar motorists spend on their vehicles, somebody (drivers, employers, local government, businesses, etc.) spend about a dollar on parking facilities for its use.

According to Simićević and Milosavljević (2023), On-street and off-street parking are the two predominant parking types. Biswas, Chandra and Ghosh (2017) stated that on-street and off-street parking issues differ in several ways. On-street parking aims to provide empty slots along the street curb, as close to motorists' destinations as possible. It can be either paid or unpaid. Payment can be manual but increasingly takes place through parking meters or other digital tools, such as smartphone apps. Pricing structures can be simple or complex or even dynamic.

According to Olorunfemi (2013), on-street parking refers to the parking space made available along the curb or shoulder of a street or road that are designed to accommodate vehicles. Kuo, Hsu, Putra and Sulistyah (2024) noted that normally, parking can occur either on the street or in designated off-street areas. On-street parking is allowed within specific zones, while off-street parking takes place in enclosed lots or garages. These parking facilities may be owned by local governments, public entities or private individuals.

Osoba (2012) stated that on-street parking constitutes one major problem that makes traffic situation chaotic in Nigerian cities. Godswill (2018) posited that the scramble for on-street parking spaces by motorists has posed serious challenge as it is arguably affecting traffic condition, volume of trips to the city, and general activities in the city centre. On-street parking is a serious problem in the area as it erodes the available street space to the extent of causing inconvenience for pedestrians, hindering traffic flow, increasing traffic accidents, impeding access to the side-walks and degrading its function to prevent disasters.

Studies by Rodrigue et.al., (2016) posited that parking space for vehicles is a major challenge in cities and has been increasing in both developed and developing countries because it links the urban transportation infrastructure, land administration, land use management and urban planning.

However, the problems of on-street parking and efficient traffic flow could be addressed through efficient off-street parking management and smart parking. According to Al-Turjman and Malekloo (2019), with the development of new technologies such as Bluetooth tags and image recognition, low-cost monitoring methods for parking lot usage have become very mature. Lin, Rivano and Le Mouel (2017) stated that this has also led to the emergence of parking APP software such as Spot Hero, J parking, ETCP, etc. in recent years allowing users to check the availability of parking spaces connected to the APP and also enabling fast parking through online payment.

Despite this array of studies on on-street parking, there is a need for research on on-street parking and sustainable traffic flow in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. It is against this background that this study focuses on on-street parking and sustainable traffic flow in Yenagoa metropolis with a view to examining the likelihood factors of on-street parking, and its implications on sustainable traffic flow within Yenagoa metropolis. The hypothesis that access to residential areas and availability of parking spaces are not likely to influence on-street parking in Yenagoa metropolis was proposed. This article is structured thus; the introduction and review of literature is presented in section 1. The convenience survey research method and area of study is presented in section 2. A discussion of results is undertaken in section 3, while section 4 concludes with recommendations.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Area

This study covers the city of Yenagoa and its suburbs or peripheral settlements. According to Ohwo (2012); Gunn and Ohwo (2022), Yenagoa is located between latitudes $4^{\circ} 55^1$ and $5^{\circ} 02^1$ and longitude $6^{\circ} 15^1$ and $6^{\circ} 25^1$. The capital city of Bayelsa State happened to be one of the confluence towns in Bayelsa State (Tamuno, 1996). According to Oyegun (1999), the city of Yenagoa is on a relatively flat plain. Its average height above sea level is less than 15m and in most places between 12m and 13m respectively. The popular dendritic drainage pattern

experienced in most deltaic region is what is obtainable in Yenagoa and its environs. The metropolis of Yenagoa spans between 5kms to 15kms in radius with Okoloba, Agudama and Akenfa to the north of Yenagoa metropolis, Edepie, Biogbolo and Imiringi to the east, Akoba, Ikibiri, Fangbe and Oweikorogha to the west and Azikoro, Elebele, Otukpoti, Emeyal and Otuogori to the south (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Yenagoa Metropolis Plannig Area

Source: Yenagoa Master Plan, 2004.

Research Methods

A cross-sectional survey research design using convenience sampling technique was adopted. Primary data on availability of parking space and its implications was obtained using structured questionnaire, while secondary data on the population of the study area was obtained from the National Population Commission data base, and the map of Yenagoa metropolis was obtained from Surveyor-General Office in Bayelsa State. The target population consists of residence of Yenagoa metropolis and commercial transport operators of tricycle, taxi and mini-buses. The operators of mass-transit, heavy duty trucks and lorries were excluded due to their insignificant contribution to on-street parking. The Taro Yamane formula of 1967 was adopted to determine the sample size of 400. The structured questionnaire was administered to motorists and commercial operators of keke, mini-bus and taxi at road junctions between Igbogene to Swali market along Mbiama-Yenagoa road using convenience random sampling, while 375 copies of questionnaire were retrieved (see Table 1). The data was analyzed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and binary logistic regression model at 0.05 significance level.

Table 1: Selected Roads/Locations

S/N	Locations	Coordinates
1	Tinacious Junction (Yenagoa-Mbiama Road)	04°57'21.3''N 006°21'39.7''E.
2	Isaac Boro Road	04°57'09.8''N 006°21'22.1''E.
3	Etegwé Junction (Yenagoa-Mbiama Road)	04°57'13.5''N 006°21'19.2''E
4	Yenagoa-Amassoma Road (Tombia)	04°57'22.4''N 006°21'24.5''E
5	Lambert Eradiri Junction (Onopa)	04°56'20.9''N 006°16'43.0''E.
6	Imgbi- Swali Market Road	04°55'30.3''N 006°16'32.7''E.
7	Winners Road, Swali	04°55'02.9''N 006°16'09.3''E.
8	Julius Berger Junction (Azikoro Town Road)	04°54'30.8''N 006°17'45.4''E.

Source: Authors' Fieldwork 2024

3. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Information on age cohorts of the respondents in Figure 2 showed that 18 respondents representing 4.8% were less than 20 years old, 93 respondents representing 24.7% were between 21-30 years old, 112 respondents representing 29.8% were between 31- 40 years old, 107 respondents representing 28.5% were between 41-50 years old, and 33 respondents representing 8.8% were between 51-60 years old, while only 2 respondents representing 0.5% were more than 70 years old.

Figure 2: Age Distribution

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2024

Traffic Flows and On-street Parking

The results of vehicular traffic flow measured as volumetric count of vehicular movement at different junctions and arterial roads in Yenagoa metropolis presented in Table 2 showed that tricycles was the dominant means of transportation with its slow speed and smaller passenger capacity coupled with intermittent stops contributes to traffic congestion which impedes traffic flow during the peak periods, followed by cars, buses and heavy-duty trucks. The observed peak periods of vehicular traffic flow or rush hours presented in Table 2 are between 7am – 9am, 1pm-2pm and 4pm – 6pm respectively. On-street parking as a result of the occupation and landuse activities of the residents of Yenagoa metropolis influenced the flow of traffic as residents rush out of their homes between 7am - 9 am, between 1pm -2pm closing period for primary schools and most offices close for the day between 4pm -6pm with vehicles parked along the streets of major roads in the metropolis. Most of the schools, hospitals, private offices and businesses are located along Yenagoa-Mbiama

Road from Igbogene to Amarata axis, the state high courts, and the local government secretariat which accommodate most civil servants in the State is located at Onopa, while almost each of the 21 communities that make up the metropolis of Yenagoa has a periodic market or a daily market where trading and commercial activities take place which encourages on-street parking and impedes traffic flow.

Effective traffic flow management such as prohibition of on-street parking, construction of modern off-street parking facilities, recover sidewalks and road setbacks to improve street space for pedestrians, enhance sustainable traffic flow, and reduces traffic accidents in Yenagoa metropolis.

Table 2: Volumetric Count of Traffic Flow

Tinacious Junction, Along Yenagoa – Mbiama Road from Igbogeneto Etegw Roundabout														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	835	1150	1135	887	795	960	740	575	690	725	1083	935	725	12030
Car	227	562	655	400	340	378	284	257	365	425	680	553	445	5571
Bus	50	120	80	70	57	65	40	75	62	135	135	115	73	1077
Isaac Boro Road By Former Glory Land Hospital Bridge Head From Etegw Roundabout To Town														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	202	405	500	402	475	555	495	428	375	360	705	720	660	6282
Car	77	188	275	265	195	220	256	200	190	229	450	480	445	3470
Bus	30	21	30	11	20	27	37	15	18	31	30	33	35	338
Paclim Filling Station, Along Yenagoa – Amassoma Road from Yenagoa to Amassoma														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	-	-	157	323	339	357	327	236	196	231	154	279	326	2925
Car	-	-	92	104	133	110	100	118	141	111	105	98	124	1236
Bus	-	-	5	26	18	23	19	25	7	24	32	19	22	220
Onopa/Lambert Eradiri Junction, Along Secretariat From/ Government House to Onopa														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	238	1074	1310	1431	1127	1105	1120	951	1024	940	948	844	480	12592
Car	22	363	670	645	510	635	667	581	625	624	619	405	170	6536
Bus	9	7	14	10	12	19	41	10	9	10	12	4	10	167
Imgbi – Swali Market Road by Jasmine Plaza from Imgbi Roundabout To Swali Market														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	675	930	1540	1390	1344	1105	975	675	730	700	690	720	730	14274
Car	81	101	134	111	135	110	466	465	465	480	495	500	490	4033
Bus	27	13	6	7	7	2	6	2	3	5	6	3	2	89
Winners Road, Swali by Atlantic Choice Hotel From Swali Market To Ox – Bow Lake Road														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	115	690	402	453	364	424	330	307	352	283	292	420	264	4696
Car	34	-	41	38	49	42	39	45	60	37	53	57	29	524
Bus	10	-	9	13	7	6	7	5	7	8	10	15	11	108
Julius Berger Junction (From Berger Junction– Azikoro Town Road)														
Vehicle	6-7am	7-8	8-9	9-10	10-11	11-12	12-1pm	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7	Total
Tricycle	315	602	303	277	198	211	215	182	335	335	340	363	90	3766
Car	113	372	155	110	88	77	80	98	175	183	120	138	35	1744
Bus	9	12	5	6	4	2	3	3	5	99	3	4	3	68

Source: Authors’ Traffic Survey 2024

Parking Space

Availability of parking space for vehicles presented in Figure 3 shows that 167 respondents representing 44.4% had space for car park in their compound, while 209(55.6%) do not have space for car park in their compound. This information corroborates findings on on-street parking of vehicles along major access roads within Yenagoa metropolis. This narrows the available road leading to vehicular traffic and gridlock. The study observed that the inability of most motorists in accessing and parking their vehicles at home is because of the marshy terrain, poor and delayed infrastructural (road) development, non-adherence to planning regulations by some developers, and a weak institutional framework for development control.

The study also observed that in areas with commercial developments, the road shoulders are used for informal sector activities. Road shoulders are part of road right-of-way which amongst other functions is used for temporary parking of vehicles. The presence of informal sector activities on road shoulders makes motorists to park far away from their desired destination for shopping or obtaining of services. Some motorists who do not consider safety still park their vehicles to obstruct traffic and sometimes cause accident. An amazing revelation by some respondents in the Akenfa area of the metropolis is that some Landlords of properties on major roads rent out the road shoulders for informal activities. Hence, the use of road shoulders with impunity and difficulty in having on-street parking space for motorists.

Figure 3: Availability of Space for Car Park

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2024

Test of Hypotheses

The ANOVA test presented in Table 3 revealed that occupation of respondents, lack of access to residences and lack of parking spaces were significant at 0.05 levels respectively.

Table 3: One-way ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.
Occupation	15.441	1	15.441	5.540	0.019
Between Groups					
Within Groups	1042.429	374	2.787		
Total	1057.870	375			
Lack Access	38.895	1	38.895	37.347	0.001
Between Groups					
Within Groups	389.506	374	1.041		
Total	428.402	375			
Lack ParkingSpace	5.978	1	5.978	4.979	0.026
Between Groups					
Within Groups	449.020	374	1.201		
Total	454.997	375			

Source: Authors’ Analysis, 2024

The result of the determinants of likelihood of on-street parking in Yenagoa metropolis revealed that lack of access to residence and lack of parking spaces was 1.8 times and 1.2 times more likely to influence on-street parking within Yenagoa metropolis (see Table 4).

Table 4: Binary Logistic Regression Model

	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(β)	95% C.I. for EXP(β)	
							Lower	Upper
Lack parking space	.247	.107	5.311	1	.021	1.280	1.038	1.578
Access to residence	.616	.114	29.125	1	.000	1.852	1.481	2.317
Place of work	-.022	.105	0.046	1	.830	.978	.796	1.201
Occupation	-.126	.071	3.186	1	.074	.882	.768	1.012
Level of education	-.418	.172	5.928	1	.015	.658	.470	.922
No setback/space	-.275	.142	3.742	1	.053	.759	.574	1.004
Constant	1.249	.753	2.750	1	.097	3.487		

Source: Authors’ Analysis, 2024

4. Conclusion

This study examined on-street parking and sustainable traffic flow in Yenagoa metropolis. A survey research design was utilized. The volumetric count of vehicular traffic at different junctions and arterial roads revealed that tricycle was the dominant means of mobility followed by cars and mini-buses. The observed peak periods of vehicular traffic flow are between 7am-9am, 1pm-2pm and 4pm-6pm. The availability of parking space, occupation of respondents and availability of access roads and road setbacks influenced sustainable traffic flow. Results revealed that occupation of respondents, lack of access roads and lack of parking spaces are significant at 0.05 levels. Binary logistic regression showed that lack of access to residence was 1.8 times more likely to influence on-street parking, while lack of parking space was 1.2 times more likely to influence on-street parking.

This study recommends efficient parking management not limited to prohibition of on-street parking, construction of modern off-street parking facilities, sidewalks and road setbacks to improve street space for pedestrians, public enlightenment on the use of road right-of-way, strengthening the institutional framework for planning and development control and provision of site and services schemes for orderly urban development. These measures will enhance sustainable traffic flow in Yenagoa metropolis.

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